

Heat Load Calculation

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this report is to provide a convenient, consistent and accurate method of calculating heating and cooling loads and to enable the designer to select systems that meet the requirement for efficient utilization and are also responsive to environmental needs. The ability to estimate loads more accurately due to changes in the calculation procedure provides a lessened margin of error. Therefore, it becomes increasingly important to survey and check more carefully the load sources, each item in the load and the effect of the system type on the load.

KEYWORDS: HVAC system, E20 program, ASHRAE standards, manual heat load calculation

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INTRODUCTION:

HEATING:

Heat is a form of energy transferred from one body, region, or thermodynamic system to another due to thermal contact when the systems are at different temperatures.

PRINCIPLES OF HEAT TRANSFER

Heat energy cannot be destroyed; it can only be transferred to another substance.

To produce cooling, heat must be removed from a substance by transferring the heat to another substance. Heat energy naturally flows from a higher-temperature substance to a lower temperature substance, in other words from hot to cold. Heat cannot be naturally flow from a cold substance to a hot substance.

METHODS OF HEAT TRANSFER

Heat energy is transferred from one substance to another substance by conduction, convection, or radiation. Conduction is the process of transferring heat through a solid and convection is the process of transferring heat as the result of the movement of a fluid. Convection often occurs as the result of the natural movement of air caused by temperature (density) differences. Radiation is the process of transferring heat by means of electromagnetic waves, emitted due to temperature difference between two objects.

Fig.1.Methods of Heat Transfer

MEASURING HEAT QUANTITY:

The unit for measuring the quantity of heat is the British thermal unit (BTU). The Btu is defined as the quantity of heat energy required to raise the temperature of 1lb of water 1 degree Fahrenheit. In SI system, heat quantity can be expressed using the unit kilo joule (KJ). Rate of heat flow is commonly expressed in terms of Btu/hr. which says that 1 Btu of heat has transferred from one substance to another during a period of 1 hour. In the SI metric system of units, the rate of heat flow is expressed in terms of kilowatts (KW).

SOURCES OF HEAT:

1. External source – Sun and Air
2. Internal sources – people, lighting, and electronics.

The manner in which a load source enters a space is indicated as

- Solar radiation through transparent surface such as windows
- Heat condition through exterior walls and roofs
- Heat conduction through interior partitions ceilings and floors
- Heat generated within the space by occupants, lights, appliances, equipment and processes
- Load as a result of ventilation and infiltration of outdoor air

Fig.2. sources of heat

PURPOSE OF HEAT LOAD CALCULATIONS:

- Provide information for equipment selection and HVAC system design.
- Provide data for evaluation of the optimum possibilities for load reduction.
- Permit analysis of partial loads as required for system design, operation and control.

HEAT LOAD ESTIMATION

There are two types of heat gain i.e. sensible heat and latent heat. Latent heat is related to change in phase between liquids, gases, and solids. Sensible heat is related to change in temperature of a gas or object with no change in phase.

Table I: Typical Diversity Factor for Large Buildings

Type of Applications	Diversity Factor	
	People	Lights
office	0.75 to 0.90	0.70 to 0.85
Apartment, hotel	0.40 to 0.60	0.30 to 0.50
Department storage	0.80 to 0.90	0.90 to 1.0
industrial	0.85 to 0.95	0.80 to 0.90

The heat load calculation is done with the basic formula i.e. $Q=U A \Delta T$

Table.2. Thermal Resistance for Building and Insulating Material

Material	K. Conductivity Btu/in/hr/sq. ft	Resistance 1/K
Marble Granite	20	0.05
Concrete	12	0.08
Brick	5	0.20
Cement Plaster	8	0.12
Wood	1	1
Glass	0.8	1.25
AC Sheet	2.7	0.37
Water	4.2	0.24
Fiber Glass	0.25	4.00
Inside film coefficient	4.00	0.25
Outside film	1.65	0.65

The U-factor for each of the type of wall is calculated according to the thickness of the wall and its thermal resistance value of each material by $U=1/\sum R$

Where,

$\sum R$ is the sum of all resistance of material inbuilt in the wall structure

1. Heat gained through radiation:

- Glass= Area * ΔT glass * U glass {value changes with direction}
- Wall= Area * ΔT wall * U wall {value changes with direction}
- Roof= Area * ΔT roof * U roof

2. Heat gained through conduction:

- Glass= Total area of all glasses * ΔT glass * U glass ($\Delta T=110 - 76^\circ F$)
- Partition/ceiling/floor= Area * ΔT * U ($\Delta T=110 - 76^\circ F - 5^\circ F$)

3. Heat gained through infiltration:

- Infiltration= Infiltration cfm * ΔT * 1.08
- Outside air= ventilation cfm * ΔT * BF * 1.08

4. Internal heat gained- sensible heat:

- People= no of people * sensible heat
- Light= Area * 2.5w * 3.41
- Appliances= W * 3.41
- **Total effective room sensible heat** = sum of 1+2+3+4.

5. Internal heat gained- latent heat:

- Infiltration= infiltration cfm * sp. Humidity*0.68
- Outside air = ventilation cfm * sp. Humidity * BF * 0.68
- People= no of people * latent heat
- **Total effective room latent heat**=_sum of 5

6. Sensible heat = ventilation cfm * temperature difference * (1 - BF) * 1.08

7. Latent heat = ventilation cfm * sp.humidity * (1 - BF) * 0.68

8. Total outside air heat = sum of 6+7

9. Grand total heat= sum of total effective room sensible heat + total effective room latent heat + total outside air heat

10. Room tonnage = grand total heat/12000

Item	Area or Quantity	Sun Gain or Temp. Diff	Factor	Btu/Hour	W	Estimate for	Summer				
						Design Conditions	DB (F)	WB (F)	RH (%)	SH Gr/Lb	
ROOM HEAT						Ambient	106	78	28	100	
ROOM SENSIBLE HEAT						Room	76	63.5	50	68	
Solar Gain - Glass						Difference	30	14.5	-22	32	
Glass - N	SqFt	x 23	F	x 0.59	0						
Glass - NE	SqFt	x 138	F	x 0.59	0						
Glass - E	SqFt	x 163	F	x 0.59	0	By Pass Factor (BF) = 0.20					
Glass - SE	SqFt	x 85	F	x 0.59	0	Contact Factor (CF = 1 - BF) = 0.80					
Glass - S	SqFt	x 14	F	x 0.59	0	CFM Ventilation					
Glass - SW	SqFt	x 85	F	x 0.59	0	CFM Per Person	2	No	= 20	= 40	
Glass - W	24	SqFt	x 163	F	x 0.59	2308	CFM Per SqFt	162	Sqft	x 0.33	= 53
Glass - NW	SqFt	x 138	F	x 0.59	0	Air Change Per Hour (CFM) =					
Skylight	SqFt	x	F	x 0.59	0	CFM	Cu.ft	1,944	x 1.5	x 1/60	= 49
Solar & Transmission Gain - Walls & Roof						CFM Infiltration					
Wall - N	SqFt	x 15	F	x 0.38	0	Swinging	x	10	c fm/door	=	-
Wall - NE	SqFt	x 21	F	x 0.38	0	Revolving Doors (People)	x	6.4	c fm/door	=	-
Wall - E	SqFt	x 29	F	x 0.38	0	Open Doors	x	1.2	c fm/door	=	-
Wall - SE	SqFt	x 29	F	x 0.38	0	Crack (feet)	20	x 0.53	c fm/ft	=	10.60
Wall - S	SqFt	x 27	F	x 0.38	0						
Wall - SW	SqFt	x 25	F	x 0.38	0	Supply CFM from Machine					
Wall - W	144	SqFt	x 23	F	x 0.38	1259	Effective Room Sensible Heat Factor =				
Wall - NW	SqFt	x 17	F	x 0.38	0	Effective Room Sensible Heat/eff Room Total Heat = 0.9083					
Roof	SqFt	x 43	F	x 0.38	0	Apparatus Dew Point (ADP)					
Transmission Gain - Except Walls & Roof						Indicated ADP (°F) =					
All Glass	24	SqFt	x 30	F	x 0.59	425	Selected ADP (°F) = 55.0				
Partition	SqFt	x 25	F	x 0.54	0	Dehumidified Rise					
Ceiling	SqFt	x	F	x	0	(Room DB - ADP) x CF = 16.80					
Floor	SqFt	x	F	x	0	DEHUMIDIFIED AIR QUANTITY					
INFILTRATION AND BY PASSED AIR						Effective Room Sensible Heat = 501 CFM					
Infiltration	11	CFM	x 30	T.Diff	x 1.08	343	Dehumidified Rise x 1.08				
Ventilation	53	CFM	x 30	T.Diff	x BF x 1.08	346					
Internal Heat						= 235 L/s					
People	2	Nos.	x 245	Btu/Hour Per Person	490	TOTAL HEAT CAPACITY					
Lighting	162	SqFt	x 2.5	W/SqFt	x 3.41	1381	Grand Total Heat = 1.03 TR				
Lighting & S. P.	SqFt	x	W/SqFt	x 3.41							
Equipment	0.50	kW	x 3410		1705						
Sub Total						8257					
Factor						5-10%	826				
Effective Room Sensible Heat						9083	SENSIBLE HEAT CAPACITY				
ROOM LATENT HEAT						Grand Sensible Heat = 1.03 TR					
Infiltration	11	CFM	x 32	Gr/Lb	x 0.68	231	12000				
Outside Air	53	CFM	x 32	Gr/Lb	x BF x 0.68	233	= MBH				
People	2	Nos.	x 205	Btu/Hour Per Person	410						
Sub Total						873					
Factor						2.5 - 5%	44	= kW			
Effective Room Latent Heat						917	Check Figures:				
EFFECTIVE ROOM TOTAL HEAT						10000	SqFt Per TR = 158				
OUTSIDE AIR HEAT						Btu/Hour Per SqFt = 12000					
Sensible	53	CFM	x 30	F(TD)	x CF x 1.08	1386	Dehumidified CFM Per SqFt = 3.09				
Latent	53	CFM	x 32	Gr/Lb	x CF x 0.68	931	Dehumidified CFM Per TR = 488				
OUTSIDE AIR TOTAL HEAT						2316					
GRAND TOTAL HEAT						12316					
Sub Total											
TONS=GRAND TOTAL HEAT/12000						1.03					

Fig.3. Heat Load Calculation using E20 sheet

CONCLUSION

1. Heat gained through radiation changes with direction.
2. Radiated heat doesn't heat the air between the sources and the object it contacts; it only heats the object itself.
3. Considering the roof till its false ceiling while calculating the heat load decreases the load on machines.
4. E20 program reduces human errors and provides accurate heat loads.
5. Ducted return air duct reduces the load on machines

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